

1142 and 1110 cm^{-1}) of the free ligand morpholine¹⁰, is also indicative of morpholine coordination to the metal ion through its nitrogen.

More or less the same conclusion can be drawn on similar grounds for lutidine¹¹ and piperidine¹² mixed ligand complexes. However, for benzylamine complex, lack of far ir and ¹³C nmr data poses some problem. Nevertheless, comparing the ir spectra of this amine mixed ligand complex with those of other complexes and supplemented by its analytical data (Table 1), it leads one to conclude that benzylamine could also be coordinating to the metal ion through its nitrogen.

In the case of naphthylthiourea complex the bands⁵ at 1580 and 1380 cm^{-1} of the phthalate ion was found to be unchanged compared to that of the starting compound nickel phthalate, which clearly indicated the absence of metal-nitrogen bond formation in the naphthylthiourea complex. The absence of metal-nitrogen bond in the naphthylthiourea complex is also evident from the appearance of unchanged NH and NH₂ bands of the free ligand¹⁴. Besides, the lowering of the C-S stretching frequency from 775 of the free ligand to 770 cm^{-1} in the complex indicates reduced double bond character of the C=S bond which is indicative of the presence of metal-sulphur bond¹⁵ in addition to the metal-oxygen bonding of the phthalate anion.

For octahedral nickel(II) complexes usually three main bands are expected at 8000-13000 (ν_1), 14000-19000 (ν_2) and 25000-30000 (ν_3) cm^{-1} arising from $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{2g}$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (F) and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions, respectively, in their electronic spectra. These absorption bands at ν_1 8.8-9, ν_2 14.5-15.5 and ν_3 25.4-25.7 kK regions were observed for the present complexes in their electronic spectra. Besides, the ratio of ν_3/ν_1 of the bands¹⁶ was found to be ~ 1.7 which also confirms the octahedral configuration for all the complexes around the metal ion.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P. C. P.) is grateful to the Management, Rourkela Steel Plant for kind help.

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Electrochemical Studies on the Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Citrulline at D.M.E.

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Manuscript received 4 May 1982, revised 12 April 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

CITRULLINE is of extreme importance in production of urea in the living body. Krebs and Henseleit¹ have shown that the synthesis of urea from ammonia and carbon dioxide in presence of intact liver tissues is markedly accelerated by the addition of citrulline. Except for a single reference of glass electrode studies by Perkins², there is no report on the chelate formation abilities of citrulline with cadmium(II) and hence the present investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solution of cadmium(II) was prepared by dissolving a weighted amount of A.R. cadmium nitrate in conductivity water. The solution was standardized as usual³. Lithium perchlorate was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Sodium salt of citrulline was used as complexing agent. The pH of solution was kept constant at 6.4 ± 0.1 . Other experimental conditions are the same as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The cathodic reduction of cadmium(II) was found to be reversible in citrulline medium as revealed by the straight line plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_{d-i}$. The result of these plots varies within 32 ± 1 mV showing two electron reduction. The diffusion controlled nature of reduction was confirmed by the proportionality of diffusion current to the square root of the effective height of mercury column. There is appreciable cathodic shift in half-wave potential of Cd(II) when test solutions containing different amount of citrulline were

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC MEASUREMENTS OF CADMIUM-CITRULLINE SYSTEM AT 303 AND 313 K
Cd(II)=0.5 mM $\mu=1.0 M (LiClO_4)$ pH=6.4±0.1

C_x (Moles)	303 K			313 K		
	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SOE)	i_d (divisions)	$F_0(X)$	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SOE)	i_d (divisions)	$F_0(X)$
0.00	0.5860	121.0	—	0.5800	121	—
0.10	0.7105	107.0	16378	0.6650	118	573
0.15	0.7260	102.0	48001	0.6755	115	1267
0.20	0.7360	98.0	104001	0.6840	112	2447
0.25	0.7420	98.0	198751	0.6915	112	4269
0.30	0.7485	92.5	341399	0.6960	112	6795
0.35	0.7545	91.0	549999	0.7015	98	10238
0.40	0.7690	90.0	1692000	0.7060	91	14729

polarographed. Further, there is a decrease in diffusion current with increase in ligand concentration. This is only due to the increase in the size of Cd(II) ion on complex formation. From the observations, it is noticed that the nature of reduction of cadmium-citrulline system remains same at 303 and 313 K though there was a little positive shift in half-wave potential values of cadmium(II) at 313 K.

The $F_0(X)$ functions of DeFord-Hume method⁶ have been plotted against C_x . A smooth curve thus obtained indicates the presence of two or more complex species in equilibrium with each other. Other derived functions i.e. $F_1(X)$, $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ when plotted against C_x gave two straight lines with slope and a straight line parallel to C_x axis, respectively. It thus confirms the formation of two consecutive complexes. The polarographic measurements and $F_0(X)$ functions are recorded in Table 1 at 303 and 313 K. The DeFord-Hume's extrapolation is depicted in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Plots of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x for Cd^{2+} -citrulline system at 303K.

Fig. 2. Plots of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x Cd^{2+} -citrulline system at 313K.

The values of overall formation constants of the 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complex species are given below:

	Overall Formation Constant (DeFord-Hume) at	
	303 K	313 K
β_1	20000	3000
β_2	300000	8000
β_3	113×10^6	1.9×10^6

From the $F_0(X)$ values at different concentrations of citrulline, the values of Mihailov's constants 'a' and 'A' were calculated at 303 K. From the average values of 'a' and 'A' the values of overall formation constants were evaluated by Mihailov's mathematical method⁶. The β_1 , β_2 and β_3 at 303 K are 11132, 428782 and 110×10^6 , respectively. There is a close proximity in the results obtained by DeFord-Hume's method and Mihailov's method.

Thermodynamic functions⁷ for 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complex species are presented in following Table:

Complex species	ΔF° k cal mole ⁻¹	ΔH° k cal mole ⁻¹	ΔS° k cal mole ⁻¹
1:1	-6.0020	-36.1895	-0.0998
1:2	-7.6029	-68.3084	-0.2003
1:3	-9.8434	-82.4532	-0.2396

It has been found in present study that Cd(II) forms 1:3 highest complex with citrulline which corroborates the hexacoordination tendency of the metal and bidentate nature of the ligand. There is no ligand field stabilization in Cd(II), hence the stereochemistry of its complexes is determined solely by consideration of size, electrostatic forces and covalent bonding forces.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the Principal and the Head, Department of Chemistry, S.G.N. Khalsa College, Sriganganagar for help and encouragement. One of the authors (B.S.S.) also thanks C.S.I.R. for award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) Complexes with Methylguanidoacetic Acid

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Manuscript received 28 July 1982, revised 18 April 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

SAXENA and coworkers¹⁻⁵ have investigated the electrochemical behaviour of some amino acids and their metal complexes which have found useful applications in biochemistry. In this communication the complexation behaviour of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions with methylguanidoacetic acid has been studied

polarographically at 25° and at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$ NaClO₄).

Experimental

Methylguanidoacetic acid [NH.C(NH₂).N(CH₃).CH₂COOH] was obtained from B.D.H., Poole, England. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Triton-X-100 (0.002%) was used as the maximum suppressor. Ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$) was maintained by NaClO₄.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the polarograms against SCE as the reference electrode. The polarograms of Cd²⁺ in presence of different concentrations of the ligand were plotted at 25° and at different pH. Well defined cathodic waves were obtained at pH 7.0 in the case of Cd²⁺ and at pH 4.0 in the case of Pb²⁺ and hence all subsequent studies were made at these pH.

To investigate the reversibility and diffusion controlled nature of the cathodic waves produced by Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with methylguanidoacetic acid, the effects of change of mercury head and concentrations of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ on the wave heights were studied. For complexation studies, a series of 1.0 mM CdSO₄ and Pb(NO₃)₂ solutions containing varying concentrations (0.02 to 0.12 M) of the ligand and 0.002% Triton-X-100 were prepared. Requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength at $\mu=0.1 M$. Half-wave potentials were obtained from the plots of $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$.

Results and Discussion

Half-wave potentials were found to shift towards the more negative values with increasing ligand concentration (Table 1) showing the complexation between Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with methylguanidoacetic acid. The appreciable differences in the diffusion currents of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions alone and in the presence of the ligand indicate that the aquo Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions differ in size of their complexes.

A plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ yielded straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. The plots of $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$ were also linear, whose slopes indicate the reversibility of the electrode reaction. A plot of $-E_{1/2}$ as a function of $-\log C_x$ showed the formation of successive complexes and hence DeFord and Hume's method was employed for determining the various complexity functions $F_j(X)$. $F'_2(X)$ vs C_x (Figs. 1 and 2) show a horizontal line parallel to the C_x axis which indicates the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes.

The plots of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$ and $F_2(X)$ vs ligand concentrations (Figs. 1 and 2), when extrapolated to $C_x=0$, gave values for the stability constants of